

ROLE OF NANOPARTICLES IN BRAIN TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY

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Abstract

Nanoparticle(NP)- drug related problems has been focused part in recent times because the reality is NP may be a problem solving aspect for the receptor stated cells either in combining form or in the healing of particle managing. BBB relates to brain pathway Endothelial cells which shows little absorptivity(endocytosis), allowing some limited precise particles like water, glucose, amino acids which are nearly permeable to BBB which reduces the brain tumor & CNS issues. Present day, due to the lack of consistency in brain drug development are most undeveloped part in qualities of CNS drug in industry. To counter the limitations regarding CNS drug transport there are some transport techniques were developed. These techniques normally divided into following categories: invasive, non-invasive or miscellaneous strategies.

Keywords: Nano-Particles, Endocytosis, Central Nervous System, Blood Brain Barrier.

INTRODUCTION

As like other dosage forms, Nanoparticle(NP)- drug related problems has been focused part in recent times because the reality is NP may be a problem solving aspect for the receptor stated cells either in combining form or in the healing of particle managing. There are certain techniques to change the medicated NP to functionalize along with ligands which acts on Blood brain barrier(BBB). Though, such techniques have strong brain related problems, so the goal is not much sure on brain microvasculature. Therefore certain updated techniques must be developed to take the opportunity related to BBB and give success as NP focused on margin, efficacy and for other aspects. At this point, we are developing a new technique whose approach is to focus on better permeability of the BBB with its endothelium.

Nature of Nano Particles:

NP are polymeric finely divided particles ranging from 10 to 100nm and are taken to medication through absorption.

The Effective Region Of Blood Brain Barrier (BBB) And Effective Drugs:

The complex approach of Brain is basically due to the endothelial, astroglia, pericyte and peri vascular mast cells, that constrict the movement of circulating cells or particles across it. The endothelial junctions of BBB plays a vital role in the ions exchange as well as protein transfer across the bio membrane of brain, it also influences the protein transfer and helps retain the surface characteristics of the mobileular surface.

The pathophysiology of brain:

There are variety of nerveous parts and tissues but the CNS is most complex tissues inside the living organism so it is like branched and long shape, complex interconnections and have very small characteristics. Cerebro vascular endothelial cells, astrocytes, neurons and pericytes are present in BBB. Paracrine connections are close by glia are prominent for smooth functioning. If Brain accidents suffering is mostly on cerebral, motor, and sensory dysfunction. Sudden and irreversible accident is dangerous to sites in brain which causes instant and irretrievable problems to the CNS and continuous accidents to the brain can cause very serious issues related to healing, which can be developed by applying some good healing tactics. It is known from Wallerian deterioration of axons, mitochondrial failure, excitotoxicity, oxidative stress and apoptotic molecular loss of spans of neurons and glia. But if the accident causes ischemic blow, haemorrhagic blow, and other damages related to brain can cause disruption of BBB, because accident cause brain tissue deficiency and have an impact on tablet response. Certain techniques created focused on endothelial cells related to BBB, to tight the junction complexes to give shape to BBB which boosts Trans Endothelial Electric resistance (TEER).

Targeting BBB

BBB relates to brain pathway Endothelial cells which shows little absorptivity (endocytosis), allowing some limited precise particles like water, glucose, amino acids which are nearly permeable to BBB which reduces the brain tumor & CNS issues. Present day, due to the lack of consistency in brain drug development are most undeveloped part in qualities of CNS drug in industry. Where as 98% of all small molecules can't cross the BBB and almost 100% large molecules can't cross the BBB which tells that no worldwide industries have BBB drug-focused programme. But towards macromolecular drug goals in brain has shows some good growth in biomedical studies and medical sciences. But on results we can tell that BBB represents one of the maximum rigid structure and complicated tissue arrangement with a feature to protect the brain from bloodborne molecules. It is vital to preserve the neurological processes. Still in case of neurological disorder, the transport of healing bioactive macromolecular combinations to altered regions of the vital anxious gadget (CNS) is notably favoured however especially it is hard to acquire, mainly whilst the overall defensive barrier feature of the BBB is to be continued.

Barriers In Mind Focused Drug Transport

The problems relate with CNS disorders can be shorted by the obstruction of drug conveyance to the CNS. There are some main limitations to flow away the extracellular fluid from the systemic circulation.

1. Blood-Brain Barrier, 2. Blood-Cerebrospinal Fluid Barrier, 3. Blood-Tumor Barrier

1) Blood - Brain Barrier (BBB) The blood

BBB is a selectively permeable part which detaches the blood from fluids present outside the cell. BBB allows water, few gases and lipid soluble molecule intake by passive diffusion.

2) Blood - Cerebrospinal Fluid Barrier (BCSFB)

It is placed at the region choroid plexus, it works with the help of blood cerebrospinal fluid barrier which detaches the blood from cerebrospinal fluid which is placed at subarachnoid area of the brain. But it is not used mostly because the uptake of medication is released at the bottom which having small surface area to release. But it is very useful to counter some bloodborne problems in CSF by the help of this barrier.

3) Blood - Tumor Barrier

Intracranial drug transport is very helpful to cure CNS tumour. For example, some primary & secondary tumours are rely on chemotherapy through CVS through intracranial trigger. But in CNS tumour all strong tumours inhibit the drug transport through CVS.

The disaster of systemically produced capsules to successfully contract with many CNS illnesses may be streamlined with the assistance of spending rational about around of boundaries that obstruct drug conveyance to the brain. At that region bodily limitations that detaches the mind extracellular fluid from the systemic circulations. 1. Blood-Brain Barrier 2. Blood-Cerebrospinal Fluid Barrier 3. Blood-Tumor Barrier

1) Blood - Brain Barrier (BBB) The blood

Brain barrier (BBB) is a particularly having selective permeable barrier that divides the socializing blood from the brain extracellular fluid withinside the vital anxious gadget. The blood – brain barrier licenses the water influx, a few gaseous material and lipophilic ingredients with the support of using passive diffusion, in addition to the discerning shipping of molecules which includes glucose and amino acids which can be central for neural feature.

2) Blood - Cerebrospinal Fluid Barrier (BCSFB)

The 2nd barrier, positioned on the choroids plexus, is signified by the of using the blood-cerebrospinal fluid obstruction which parts the blood part from the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) which, in turn, runs withinside the subarachnoid area adjacent at the mind. So, this wall isn't always taken into consideration as a foremost path of influx of medication seeing that the bottom area is too smaller than BBB. CSF part can have another molecules at the interstitial fluid of the brain parenchyma, the road of bloodborne particles into the CSF is likewise controlled by the help of using the BCB.

4) Blood - Tumor Barrier

Intracranial transport is superior hard whilst the goal is a CNS disorder. For example, even if primary and secondary tumors reply to chemotherapy dealers brought through the cardio gadget, intracranial part frequently keep growing. In CNS related disorders in which the BBB is extensively compromised, lots of limitations not unusual place to all strong tumors inhibit drug transport through the cardiovascular gadget.

Mechanisms of Influx of Drug Through BBB

Medicaments can go by the BBB by using certain mchanusms like-transmembrane(across) diffusion, saturable shipping, adsorptive endocytic process and extracellular related parts.

1) Transmembrane Diffusion

Mostly medicaments can go through BBB through this mechanism.It is a different mechanism which depend on drug fusion into mobileular membrane.Mostly low molecular weight and lipid soluble drugs can cross BBB by this mechanism.

2) Saturable Transport System

Some medicaments can go through BBB by this mechanism. E.g., L-DOPA and caffeine.The uptake of medicaments through BBB is 10 times faster in this mechanism as compare to others.

Problems Confronted In Brain Focused Drug Transport

There are chances of a medicament that can't cross the BBB or can mobilize during this way. It is due to the drug can change its form which permits a small amount of reaction and skips the BBB and may also be due to the binding with other proteins inside the body which makes the medicament's efficacy weak which leads to the omission of BBB and some enzymes also inhibit the efficacy. These issues must be countered to increase the efficacy regarding brain tissues.

Approaches For Brain Focused Drug Transport

To counter the limitations regarding CNS drug transport, there are some transport techniques that were developed. These techniques are normally divided into the following categories: invasive, non-invasive, or miscellaneous strategies.

A. Invasive

- Intracerebroventricular (ICV) infusion
- Convection-mediated transport (CED)
- Intra-cerebral injection or implants
- Disruption of the BBB.

B. Non-invasive

- Chemical strategies
 - a) Prodrug
- Colloidal Techniques
 - a) Nanoparticles
 - b) Liposomes.

C. Miscellaneous strategies

- Intranasal transport

A. Invasive Approach medicaments may be redesigned to make a newer approach which inserts inside the brain, after which it can be placed by the help of using intracerebral (IC) or infusion is given with the help of using intracerebroventricular (ICV).

Thus each huge and small molecules may be carried.

- 1) Intra-cerebro-ventricular infusion
- 2) Convection-more advantageous transport
- 3) Intracerebral Implants
- 4) Disruption of the BBB

1. Intra-cerebro-ventricular infusion (ICV) It is being proved that the drug intake withinside the brain is simplest 1–2% of the CSF care at simply 1–2 mm from the floor.

Limitations The drug diffusion withinside parenchyma part may be very less. So aim is near the ventricular region it isn't always a green technique of drug transport.

2. Convection-more advantageous transport (CED) The popular transport of CED attached the purposefully which helps in inclusion of a little-quality tube into parenchymatic cell. By this tube, insertion is driven upto mind parenchymatic cell and which allows at withinside the interstitial region.

Limitations Some areas of the mind are tough to fill absolutely with infuscate, specially permeated tissues adjoining a void. Proper drug allocation hang up upon by the adjustment of catheters.

3. Intra-cerebral injection are helps in implants Delivery of medicaments into the brain parenchymatic region, medicine may managed with the aid of using:

- Insertion through intrathecal catheter.
- Controlling the launch channel.
- Microencapsulated chemical compounds.

Limitations Spreading withinside brain with the help of using diffusion decreases mostly with distance. The injection web website online needs to be properly planned to get accuracy and overcome the problem related to distribution of medicine withinside the brain parenchymatic cell.

4. Disruption of the BBB It approach is carried mostly for CNS medicament transport which causes breaking of the BBB. Insertion to X radiation and intake of solvents which contains dimethyl sulfoxide, ethanol part can also interrupt BBB.

Osmotic disruption osmosis process arises endothelial cells to be smaller, which break the tough adjacents. Intracarotid management of a hypertonic mannitol causes next supervision medication can make high the medicaments efficacy in CNS and affected tissue to show more sharpness.

MRI-guided centered ultrasound BBB disruption-Ultrasound process can also to be causes BBB problems. Mixture of microbubbles (examined microbubbles shows ultrasound evaluation agent, with a diameter range of 2-6 μm that is inserted into the blood progress earlier than displays to examine through ultrasound). Procedure has been detailed to high the circulation of Herceptin in CNS tissue with the support of using animal model.

Limitations of this part

- Every approaches are high cost, allows anaesthesia and hospitalization.
- like this approaches can also moreover remodel tumour distribution after a success disruption of the BBB.

B. Non-invasive strategies

In this part drug transport procedure was searched, transport the total blood community for drug releasing. Non-invasive strategies mainly relied upon drug exchange which can also additionally show some changes as:

- Chemical strategies
 - a) Prodrug
- Colloidal Techniques
 - a) Nanoparticles
 - b) Liposomes
- Chemical approach

a. Prodrug that is lipid soluble and may pass through the BBB. Prodrug is transformed withinside brain and changes to the figure drug. Except by deacetylation of morphine to form heroin. Prodrugs are nonreactive compounds.

Colloidal Techniques The vesicular structures are particularly gathered of 1 or lots of concentric lipid bilayer shaped, whilst sure amphiphilic products are faced with water. Extend the span of the medicament in blood, and which decreases the toxins of influx may made because of allowance of medicament immediately at site of infection. Advances the medicaments rate and extent mainly within the phase of non-lipophilic drugs.

A. Nanoparticles

These Nanoparticles (NPs) are rigid having smaller ingredients comprises of some morphs having in length from 1-one thousand nm which comprises of individually nano capsules, with a centre cap shape, and some nanospheres. These are acts as a carrier wherein the medicaments is processed through some processes like dissolved, entrapped, encapsulated, adsorbed.

Nanoparticle preparation in CNS intensive drug curing needs higher penetration of therapeutic and problem-solving sellers, and less threat in difference for standard treatments. Using this technology, it's likely to transport the drug to the site throughout the BBB, the dissolution of medicament at a control rate which shows good efficacy. decreasing of toxins at side organs and biodegradation also will be examined at those part.

Mechanism- It for distribution of lipid-protein to be endocytic by the help of Low Density Lipoprotein (LDL) receptor after adsorption of lipoproteins in the body fluid to the nanoparticles. This is usually processed about mechanism with lipoprotein receptors is acts for the brain uptake of the medicament.

Advantages of the use of nanoparticles for CNS focused drug transport

- These are counters capsules through chemical and enzymatic degradation.
- Because of their small size nanoparticles can allows into small regions and are uptake at inside cells, countering medicaments gathering which related to Degradation.

Limitations of the work of nanoparticles for CNS focused drug transport

Their small length can cause particle-particle aggregation, forms bodily managing of nanoparticles hard in liquid and dry forms.

Example Polyethylene glycol lined hexadecyl cyanoacrylate nanospheres focused and cumulative in a rat having liposarcoma. But the technique isn't always but can use for medical trials because of the formation of the nanotechnologies at the adjacent healthful sites.

B. Liposomes

These are mainly related totally vesicular which are microscopic (unilamellar or multilamellar) vesicles which can be made due to self-meeting of phospholipids in an water medium closed double structures. Meanwhile lipophilic membrane gathered at middle, each hydro and lipophilic soluble capsules may be formed liposomes.

These medicaments very sharp withinside the bilayer membrane while water soluble or hydrophilic medicaments closed withinside the hydro mid part of the vesicles. These are good in service to managed medicament transport of brain cancers, for gene and with medication by nucleic acid transportation, immunity enhancement by antigen transport, antiParkinson's disease.

Advantages

- It shows each lipid soluble gathered and watery "milieu interne" at a single form and are accordingly transport of hydrophobic, amphipathic, and hydrophilic medicaments.

- Liposome need to incorporate which is not easy small molecules however additionally macromolecules like superoxide dismutase, haemoglobin, erythropoietin, interleukin2 and interferon-g.

Limitations

- High costly
- Leak and merge of encapsulated drug / molecules.
- Occasionally phospholipid along with oxidation and hydrolysis

C. Miscellaneous strategies

Some Intranasal drug transportation are source in nasal cavity. Nasal mucosa helps in handing over medicine for brain issues and local effect management of analgesics, sedatives, hormones, cardiovascular capsules, and vaccines, corticosteroid hormones.

Mechanism for transporting certain mechanisms which acts at the direct nostril medicament transport: a. Intracellular transporting medium is there b. Extracellular transporting mediated sites. The intracellular shipping process is very tedious process, time for intra nasal insertion materials to release at the olfactory bulb. Extracellular transporting is very rapid.

Advantages

- fast drug release is at vascular mucosa.
- Medicaments which can't release orally can be processed through nasal drug transport.

Disadvantages of intranasal drug transport

- Some medicaments can also attain contamination to the nasal mucosa
- Nasal congestion because of bloodless or hypersensitive adverse reactions can also additionally implemented with absorption of drug.

Advance techniques:

1) Dendrimers

2) Scaffolds

3) Lipoplexes and Polyplexes

4) Polyanhydrides

5) Modified nanoparticles

- Multifunctional nanoparticles
- Magnetic nanoparticles.

6) Receptor-mediated shipping (RMT)

- Monoclonal antibody (MAb) molecular Trojan horses (MTH)
- Trojan horse liposomes for CNS gene remedy
- In vivo mind imaging of gene expression

7) Transporter-unbiased mechanisms to avoid the BBB

- Convection-more advantageous drug transport (CED)
- Ultrasound-mediated BBB opening.
- Bradykinin receptor-mediated BBB opening

Recent Advances In Brain Targeting

1. Dendrimers

These are grouped polymeric substances, comes having a shape of a tree. It is usually symmetric at the middle, whereas mostly lengthy which continuously relates a sphere shaped in water. One part may shows the figure as a minimum same chemical structures and functions; opening from those groups, repeated gadgets of unlike molecules can be formed, having as a minimum one junction of branching.

2. Scaffolds

Scaffolds are implantable and may be countered with lots of difficulties connected to brain injury and illnesses, for handing over medications to deal with neurological diseases which comprises Parkinson's disorder and Alzheimer's disorder. Transporting of from here undoubtedly allows to control the harm at the same time helps as to control their feature.

3. Lipoplexes and Polyplexes

For increase transport of brand-new DNA into the mobileular, DNA have countered from EGRADATION and its allows AT the mobileular have to active. Lipoplexes and polyplexes shows this allowance. To counter the DNA from unwanted degradation for a certain period of process. DNA may concern with lipoproteins in a wanted shape as micelle or a liposome. But the formed shape merged with DNA it is referred to as a lipoplex. There are mostly 3 sorts of lipids.

- Anionic (negatively charged)
- Neutral
- Cationic (charged)

4. Polyanhydrides at brain tumor shows Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) obligations around most of person number one mind tumors and are examined withinside the cerebrum. Many of the cancers medications have large shapes, ionic price or are water loving and for that cause are not able to go through the BBB, and impossibly have large are obligatory to get the curative doses withinside the CNS.

5. Modified nanoparticles

The procedure of this part as a course to brain medicament carriage has the succeeding lead.

- Exceptional good
- less-toxic and less reactive.
- Manageable loading/producing energetic (capsules/assessment dealers)
- Targeted delivery obtain conveyance as massive part for curing..

CONCLUSION

Carrying drugs efficiently for curing of brain linked disorders are exaggerated by less of knowledge and efficient advanced methods. Despite these difficulties, important development were in the plans for CNS concerned drugs. But nothing were showed is as effective. Which resulted by this review article that which means of this methods where medicaments can pass the BBB. Fresh methods related to passing BBB have shows mostly obliging to countering blocks related with brain related part. Thus, this part shows more efficacy which targeting shows a better clinical competence and efficacy but still we need most reliable approaches which have high scientific efficacy and economical.

References

- 1) Kaur I P et al 2008 Potential of solid lipid nanoparticles in brain targeting J. Control. Release 127 97–109
- 2) Abbott N J et al 2010 Structure and function of the blood-brain barrier Neurobiol. Dis. 37 13–25
- 3) Sahni J K et al 2011 Neurotherapeutic applications of nanoparticles in Alzheimer's disease J. Control. Release 152 208–31
- 4) Pardridge, W.M. Why is the global CNS pharmaceutical market so underpenetrated? Drug Discov. Today 7, 5–7 (2002)
- 5) Pardridge, W.M. Brain Drug Targeting: The Future of Brain Drug Development, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, U.K. (2001)
- 6) Ajay, Bemis, G.W., and Murcko, M.A. Designing libraries with CNS activity. J. Med. Chem. 42, 4942–4951 (1999).
- 7) Ghose, A.K., Viswanadhan, V.N., and Wendoloski, J.J. A knowledge-based approach in designing combinatorial or medicinal chemistry libraries for drug discovery.
- 8) A qualitative and quantitative characterization of known drug databases. J. Comb. Chem. 1, 55–68 (1999). Analysis of over 7000 drugs in Comprehensive Medicinal Chemistry database showing only 5% of drugs treat the brain and these drugs only treat 3 disorders (depression, schizophrenia, insomnia).
- 9) Agrawal M, Saraf S, Saraf S, et al. Recent advancements in the field of nanotechnology for the delivery of anti-Alzheimer drug in the brain region. Expert Opin Drug Deliv. 2018;15(6):589–617.

- 10) Singh AV, Chandrasekar V, Janapareddy P, et al. Emerging Application of Nanorobotics and Artificial Intelligence To Cross the BBB: advances in Design, Controlled Maneuvering, and Targeting of the Barriers. *ACS Chem Neurosci*. 2021;1:448–455.
- 11) Aderibigbe BA. In situ-based gels for nose to brain delivery for the treatment of neurological diseases. *Pharmaceutics*. 2018;10(2):40. doi:10.3390/pharmaceutics10020040
- 12) Mandal S, Vishvakarma P. Nanoemulgel: A Smarter Topical Lipidic Emulsion-based Nanocarrier. *Indian J of Pharmaceutical Education and Research*. 2023;57(3s):s481-s498.
- 13) Mandal S, Jaiswal DV, Shiva K. A review on marketed Carica papaya leaf extract (CPLE) supplements for the treatment of dengue fever with thrombocytopenia and its drawback. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2020 Jul;12(3).
- 14) Mandal S, Bhumika K, Kumar M, Hak J, Vishvakarma P, Sharma UK. A Novel Approach on Micro Sponges Drug Delivery System: Method of Preparations, Application, and its Future Prospective. *Indian J of Pharmaceutical Education and Research*. 2024;58(1):45-63.
- 15) Mishra, N., Alagusundaram, M., Sinha, A., Jain, A. V., Kenia, H., Mandal, S., & Sharma, M. (2024). Analytical Method, Development and Validation for Evaluating Repaglinide Efficacy in Type II Diabetes Mellitus Management: a Pharmaceutical Perspective. *Community Practitioner*, 21(2), 29–37. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10642768>
- 16) Singh, M., Aparna, T. N., Vasanthi, S., Mandal, S., Nemade, L. S., Bali, S., & Kar, N. R. (2024). Enhancement and Evaluation of Soursop (*Annona Muricata* L.) Leaf Extract in Nanoemulgel: a Comprehensive Study Investigating Its Optimized Formulation and Anti-Acne Potential Against *Propionibacterium Acnes*, *Staphylococcus Aureus*, and *Staphylococcus Epidermidis* Bacteria. *Community Practitioner*, 21(1), 102–115. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10570746>
- 17) Khalilullah, H., Balan, P., Jain, A. V., & Mandal, S. (n.d.). Eupatorium Rebaudianum Bertoni (STEVIA): Investigating Its Anti-Inflammatory Potential Via Cyclooxygenase And Lipooxygenase Enzyme Inhibition - A Comprehensive Molecular Docking And Admet. *Community Practitioner*, 21(03), 118–128. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10811642>
- 18) Mandal, S. (n.d.). Gentamicin Sulphate Based Ophthalmic Nanoemulgel : Formulation And Evaluation , Unravelling A Paradigm Shift In Novel Pharmaceutical Delivery Systems. *Community Practitioner*, 21(03). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10811540>
- 19) Mandal, S., Tyagi, P., Jain, A. V., & Yadav, P. (n.d.). Advanced Formulation and Comprehensive Pharmacological Evaluation of a Novel Topical Drug Delivery System for the Management and Therapeutic Intervention of Tinea Cruris (Jock Itch). *Journal of Nursing*, 71(03). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10811676>
- 20) Zhang L, Yao K, Wang Y, et al. Brain-Targeted Dual Site- Selective Functionalized Poly (β -Amino Esters) Delivery Platform for Nerve Regeneration. *Nano Lett*. 2021;21 (7):3007–3015. doi:10.1021/acs.nanolett.1c00175
- 21) Ng SY, Lee AYW. Traumatic brain injuries: pathophysiology and potential therapeutic targets. *Front Cell Neurosci*. 2019;13:528. doi:10.3389/fncel.2019.00528
- 22) Chodobski A, Zink BJ, Szmydynger-Chodobska J. Blood–brain barrier pathophysiology in traumatic brain injury. *Transl Stroke Res*. 2011;2(4):492–516. doi:10.1007/s12975-011-0125-x
- 23) Cantrill CA, Skinner RA, Rothwell NJ, Penny JI. An immortalised astrocyte cell line maintains the in vivo phenotype of a primary porcine in vitro blood–brain barrier model. *Brain Res*. 2012;1479:17–30. doi:10.1016/j.brainres.2012.08.031
- 24) Lam C, Hansen E, Janson C, Bryan A, Hubel A. The characterization of arachnoid cell transport II: paracellular transport and blood–cerebrospinal fluid barrier formation. *Neuroscience*. 2012;222:228–238. doi:10.1016/j.neuroscience.2012.06.065
- 25) Ayloo S, Gu C. Transcytosis at the blood–brain barrier. *Curr Opin Neurobiol*. 2019;57:32–38. doi:10.1016/j.conb.2018.12.014 20. Lu W. Adsorptive-mediated brain delivery systems. *Curr Pharm Biotechnol*. 2012;13(12):2340–2348. doi:10.2174/1389201128033 41851